

Edge architecture for cooperative mobile manipulators handling and planning

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Abstract—Mobile manipulators have been getting employed in industrial scenarios more often in recent years. This is due to their huge dexterity, the high amount of degree of freedom, and their ability to move freely in the working space. Having a huge redundancy makes it difficult for the planning algorithm to devise a plan, especially when multiple mobile robots are involved and their navigation is constrained. On the other hand, the robotic arm mounted on top can compensate for the navigation path following errors, but require prompt error estimation and low communication latency in the whole system.

Index Terms—Mobile manipulators, cooperative planning, distributed control, cloud computing, computer vision

I. INTRODUCTION

Industrial Mobile Manipulators (IMMs) have seen a substantial industrial employment increase in the latest years, thanks to their extensive dexterity and applicability in many scenarios. This dexterity comes as a result of embedding Industrial robots (IRs) systems, on top of an AMR, resulting in a complex kinematic chain that relies on the AMR positioning capability and the IR dexterity. When it comes to planning a path involving multiple mobile manipulators, each robot's plan has to keep distance and orientation constraints to the others, in order to preserve the overall kinematic chain comprised of the mobile manipulators and the handled object. At the same time, the overall state of the system must be known accurately, to be able to command each mobile manipulator accordingly and control the kinematic error dynamic. This problem might be considered as part of the formation control problem [1] or solved as a distributed optimization problem as in [2]. In order to tackle this problem, our proposal includes an edge-based architecture in order to plan and control the whole system efficiently.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

Consider a couple of mobile manipulators whose goal is to transport a semi-rigid object from a starting point to an ending point. To perform this, an initial global plan will be devised for each of the involved mobile manipulators, in order to preserve the kinematic constraints of the handled object, and avoid obstacles in the path. Once the suitable plans for each robot involved are found, each robot has to follow the waypoints of the plan in a cooperative manner, keeping the kinematic constraints satisfied throughout the navigation, as shown in fig 1. During the navigation, the system has to constantly estimate

Figure 1: Global plan(top) and local plan(bottom)

the state of each mobile manipulator, in order to compensate for errors and act on the elements.

III. ARCHITECTURE

The overall architecture is shown in fig 2. Each robot is endowed with a low-level controller for the base motors and the robot, in order to follow the received local plans. The local sensor readings are constantly forwarded to the edge server for plan computation and state identification. The edge server is in charge of the global plan craft and constant monitoring of the state and feeds local plan updates to the local robots. While the global plan is unique, the local one is constantly updated to optimize the overall robustness, taking advantage of each robot's high number of degrees of freedom.

IV. GLOBAL PLANNING

In order to compute a global plan for both the IMM, the edge server receives the kinematic description of each IMM,

Figure 2: Plan and control architecture

the kinematic constraint imposed by the transported object, and the environmental information. The plan is computed in such a way to optimize each robot’s robustness to external disturbances, such as obstacles, and localization errors. To do so, the robots’ high degree of freedom is leveraged in order to choose a high dexterity and flexible joint configuration.

A. Mobile manipulator optimization

In order to plan an “easy to reconfigure” path, the high number of degrees of freedom present in the system can be taken advantage of. The optimization criteria leverage the mounted robotic arm to maintain the kinematic constraints during the movements, and to correct errors coming from localization and navigation inaccuracies, taking into account the overall kinematic uncertainty and the localization errors. Furthermore, the optimization has to include also information about the goal position, also considering the kinematic constraints of the goal position of the transported object.

V. LOCAL PLANNING

Once the global plan is computed, the local plan creates the actual velocity command for each robot with the aim of following precisely the global plan. The quality of the computed local command is proportional to the status knowledge, the kinematic precision, and localization; hence, a continuous estimation of the overall state is needed in order to stabilize the

system. The computed local plans are then sent to each IMM and constantly monitored by the edge server, in order to correct the values depending on the localization errors through the navigation. Following this paradigm, both local plans can be updated, or a master-slave scenario can be pursued by acting only on one platform’s path while making the other act as a master.

VI. SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT AND TRIALS

In order to test the future developed frameworks and algorithms, a complete system is being developed by STIMA LEONARDO, comprised by two mobile manipulators. The future test case will be part of the LAMPO project, in which a set of two mobile manipulators will be employed in a LEONARDO facility to move a semi-rigid carbon sheet from a deposit zone to a formation stamp. Both robots will be endowed with a 6 degrees of freedom robots and an omnidirectional mobile robot. The complete scenario will be comprised of a navigation to grasp position phase, a cooperative transportation phase, and a mounting phase into a carbon sheet mold.

REFERENCES

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